

Aligning storage operation with the environmental goal of reducing carbon emissions

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Abstract

Energy storage is crucial for integrating intermittent renewables, but its operation does not always align with the environmental goal of reducing carbon emissions. This paper proposes and evaluates a novel carbon-aware mechanism designed to steer storage operations towards emission reduction within the context of Italy's new time-shifting (TS) market. We introduce a system of financial rewards and penalties for TS contract holders based on the grid's average carbon intensity at the time of charging and discharging. Using a detailed model of the Italian electricity market and real-world data, we simulate the impact of this mechanism. The results show that the proposed scheme can help reduce carbon emissions, achieving a 3.5% decrease at the national level and reductions of up to 13% in specific high-emission zones. These findings demonstrate that incorporating explicit carbon pricing signals into storage market mechanisms is an effective strategy to ensure that energy storage assets contribute positively to decarbonisation efforts.

Keywords: energy storage; investment; carbon emission;

1. Introduction

Energy storage is an essential technology to help enable the massive deployment of intermittent renewable that is required to reach net zero. However, the current financial incentives for locating and operating storage do not necessarily align with the environmental goal of reducing carbon emissions. Indeed, energy trading by battery owners may end up increasing emissions in power grids by shifting the generation mix towards dirtier sources (Beuse et al., 2021; Savelli et al., 2025). Therefore, it is critical to design new mechanisms to help steer the decision-making process of storage investors towards climate-friendly operations.

Recently, a new mechanism to incentivise storage deployment has been introduced in Italy. It is based on two interlinked elements, i.e. an auction to incentivise storage investment, termed mechanism for procuring energy storage capacity (MACSE), which is coupled with an additional market for selling time-shifting contracts, whose revenues help fund the MACSE (RSE, 2024). In detail, through MACSE, investors receive from the transmission system operator a fixed payment to build and maintain their assets. However, they cannot freely operate their storage. Indeed, one of the key elements of this scheme is that the operation of the storage (i.e. the decision to charge or discharge the storage by withdrawing or injecting power into the grid) is auctioned in a time-shifting market.

Time-shifting (TS) contracts grant their holders the right to control a virtual storage system, allowing them to withdraw energy from the grid and store it, for subsequent re-injection into the grid. This implies that the actual storage owner cannot freely operate its asset. Instead, it is obliged to maintain and keep the storage capacity readily available, and operate the asset according to the instruction of the transmission system operator that

results from the net TS contract holders' decisions. Time-shifting contracts can span different periods, ranging from one day to several years. Moreover, TS contracts with a residual life shorter than the original one can be converted into shorter-term contracts and resold in secondary auctions.

TS contracts are purchased on a specific platform managed by the Italian market operator. The market operator collects all revenues from auctioning TS contracts and passes them to the transmission system operator, who in turn uses this amount to finance storage owners through MACSE auctions.

In this work, we introduce into the TS market a carbon-aware mechanism by explicitly accounting for the average carbon intensity at the time of charging and discharging. In detail, TS contract holders receive a payment if they decide to discharge (charge) at hours when the expected carbon intensity is above (below) the average. Instead, they have to pay if they charge (discharge) at hours when the expected carbon intensity is above (below) the average. The results show that the proposed mechanism can reduce the average carbon emission by more than 3%.

2. Models

This section describes the mathematical models that have been used to: i) reproduce the TS auctions (Section 2.1), ii) determine the TS contract holders' charging and discharging patterns (Section 2.2), and iii) perform the day-ahead market clearing to determine the market price and the average carbon emission intensity (Section 2.3).

2.1. TS contract auction

TS contracts are auctioned by the Italian electricity market operator, while the total amount supplied S_n^{TS} for each zone n is decided by the transmission system operator (who also receives the collected revenues). In the following TS auction model, each market participant $k \in K_n^{TS}$ is willing to buy TS contracts for a maximum capacity $e_{n,k}^{TS,max}$ at an offer price $o_{n,k}$. The objective of the TS auction is to allocate the overall storage capacity, while maximising the collected revenues, as follows:

$\max_{e_{n,k}^{TS}} \sum_{k \in K_n^{TS}} o_{n,k} e_{n,k}^{TS}$		(1.1)
s. t.		
$e_{n,k}^{TS} \leq e_{n,k}^{TS,max}$	$\forall n \in N, \forall k \in K_n^{TS}$	(1.2)
$\sum_{k \in K_n^{TS}} e_{n,k}^{TS} \leq S_n^{TS}$	$\forall n \in N$	(1.3)

The term $e_{n,k}^{TS}$ represents the storage capacity allocated to the contract holder k . Constraint (1.2) allows for partially executed orders, while constraint (1.3) guarantees that the overall capacity allocated in the auction respects the limit S_n^{TS} determined by the transmission system operator.

2.2. TS holder charging and discharging patterns

In the following, we assume that each TS holder k in zone n has its own forecast of the day-ahead market prices $\lambda_t^{k,n}$, which it uses to determine the optimal charging and discharging patterns by solving the following maximisation problem of the day-ahead arbitrage profits:

$\max_{\substack{p_{t,n,k}^{d,TS,max}, \\ p_{t,n,k}^{g,TS,max}, e_{t,n,k}}} \sum_{t \in T} \lambda_t^{k,n} (p_{t,n,k}^{g,TS,max} - p_{t,n,k}^{d,TS,max})$		(2.1)
s. t.		
$e_{t,n,k} = e_{t-1,n,k} + (\eta_k p_{t,n,k}^{d,TS,max} - p_{t,n,k}^{g,TS,max}) \Delta_t$	$\forall t \in T$	(2.2)
$0 \leq e_{t,n,k} \leq e_{n,k}^{TS}$	$\forall t \in T$	(2.3)
$0 \leq p_{t,n,k}^{d,TS,max} \leq b_{t,n,k} e_{k,n}^{TS} / h$	$\forall t \in T$	(2.4)
$0 \leq p_{t,n,k}^{g,TS,max} \leq (1 - b_{t,n,k}) e_{k,n}^{TS} / h$	$\forall t \in T$	(2.5)
$\sum_{t \in T} p_{t,n,k}^{g,TS,max} \leq e_{k,n}^{TS}$		(2.6)

with $e_{0,n,k} = e_{24,n,k} = 0$. The objective function (2.1) maximises the arbitrage profits, where the parameter $\lambda_t^{k,n}$ is the expected price in zone n at time t by user k , while $p_{t,n,k}^{g,TS,max}$ and $p_{t,n,k}^{d,TS,max}$ are the discharging and charging decision variables, respectively. Equation (2.2) defines the energy storage dynamics, where the current energy stored $e_{t,n,k}$ depends on the energy in the previous period $e_{t-1,n,k}$, and the power charged $p_{t,n,k}^{d,TS,max}$ and discharged $p_{t,n,k}^{g,TS,max}$, with round-trip efficiency η_k and $\Delta_t = 1$ hour. Constraints (2.3)-(2.5) sets the limits for the stored energy, charging and discharging power, respectively, where $b_{t,n,k}$ is a binary variable to prevent the simultaneous charging and discharging, $e_{k,n}^{TS}$ is the capacity allocated in the TS auction determined in the problem (1) and h is the storage duration, defined as the energy to power ratio. Finally, constraint (2.6) limits the number of storage cycles to one per day.

2.3. Day-ahead market clearing

Given the charging $p_{t,n,k}^{d,TS,max}$ and discharging $p_{t,n,k}^{g,TS,max}$ patterns determined in the problem (2), TS holders submit their bids to the day-ahead market, which determine the cleared quantity and market prices, as follows:

$\max_{\substack{p_{t,k}^d, p_{t,k}^{d,TS}, \\ p_{t,k}^g, p_{t,k}^{g,TS}, f_{t,i,j}}} \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{n \in N} \left(\sum_{k \in K_n^d} c_{t,n,k}^d p_{t,n,k}^d + \sum_{k \in K_n^{TS}} c_{t,n,k}^{d,TS} p_{t,n,k}^{d,TS} - \sum_{k \in K_n^g} c_{t,n,k}^g p_{t,n,k}^g - \sum_{k \in K_n^{TS}} c_{t,n,k}^{g,TS} p_{t,n,k}^{g,TS} \right)$		(3.1)
s. t.		
$p_{t,n,k}^d \leq p_{t,n,k}^{d,max}$	$\forall t \in T, \forall n \in N, \forall k \in K_n^d$	(3.2)
$p_{t,n,k}^{d,TS} \leq p_{t,n,k}^{d,TS,max}$	$\forall t \in T, \forall n \in N, \forall k \in K_n^{TS}$	(3.3)
$p_{t,n,k}^g \leq p_{t,n,k}^{g,max}$	$\forall t \in T, \forall n \in N, \forall k \in K_n^g$	(3.4)
$p_{t,n,k}^{g,TS} \leq p_{t,n,k}^{g,TS,max}$	$\forall t \in T, \forall n \in N, \forall k \in K_n^{TS}$	(3.5)
$-f_{t,i,j}^{max} \leq f_{t,i,j} \leq f_{t,i,j}^{max}$	$\forall t \in T, \forall (i,j) \in \mathcal{L}$	(3.6)
$\sum_{k \in K_n^d} p_{t,n,k}^d + \sum_{k \in K_n^{TS}} p_{t,n,k}^{d,TS} - \sum_{k \in K_n^g} p_{t,n,k}^g - \sum_{k \in K_n^{TS}} p_{t,n,k}^{g,TS} = \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{L}} a_{i,j,n} f_{t,i,j}$	$\forall t \in T, \forall n \in N$	(3.7)

where the decision variables are the cleared demand $p_{t,n,k}^d$ and generation $p_{t,n,k}^g$, the power flow $f_{t,i,j}$, and the accepted charging and discharging quantities $p_{t,n,k}^{d,TS}$ and $p_{t,n,k}^{g,TS}$. The objective function (3.1) maximises the

overall welfare given the bid prices $c_{t,n,k}^d$, $c_{t,n,k}^g$, $c_{t,n,k}^{d,TS}$ and $c_{t,n,k}^{g,TS}$ from consumers, generators and TS holders, respectively. Constraints (3.2)-(3.6) set the limits on the decision variables, while equation (3.7) is the power balance. As a result of the market clearing, we determine the generation mix, which is used to compute the average carbon emission intensity (kgCO2/MWh) by using the carbon intensity for each technology listed in Table 1.

Technology	kgCO2/MWh
Biomass	120
DSR/Emb. gen.	0
Fossil Coal-derived gas	872
Fossil Gas	394
Fossil Hard coal	937
Fossil Oil	935
Geothermal	0
Hydro Pumped Storage	0
Hydro Run-of-river and poundage	0
Hydro Water Reservoir	0
Other	300
Solar	0
Waste	593
Wind Offshore	0
Wind Onshore	0
Gas CCGT	394
Gas OCGT	651
Nuclear	0

Table 1 Carbon emission intensity for each technology.

3. The proposed scheme

We propose to enhance the TS market by adding a mechanism to incentivise environment-friendly storage operation by providing either a monetary reward or a penalty to TS holders depending on the carbon intensity at the time of operation. In detail, each TS contract holder receives a payment if they decide to discharge (charge) at hours when the carbon intensity is above (below) the average. Instead, they have to pay if they charge (discharge) at hours when the expected carbon intensity is above (below) the average. Using the average carbon emission as the reference point helps maintain the scheme self-funded. Given the monetary flows $\gamma_{t,n}^g$ and $\gamma_{t,n}^d$ decided by regulators, an investor k will determine how to operate the storage by solving the following profit maximisation problem, similarly to (2), with the only difference that the objective function will be defined as:

$\max_{\substack{p_{t,n,k}^{d,TS,max}, \\ p_{t,n,k}^{g,TS,max}, e_{t,n,k}}} \sum_{t \in T} (\lambda_t^{k,n} + \gamma_{t,n}^g) p_{t,n,k}^{g,TS,max} - \sum_{t \in T} (\lambda_t^{k,n} + \gamma_{t,n}^d) p_{t,n,k}^{d,TS,max}$	(4.1)
s.t.	
(2.2) - (2.6)	(4.2)

4. Results

To test the proposed mechanism, we use actual data from the Italian electricity market operator referring to July 1st, 2023 (GME, 2023). The values of the monetary flows $\gamma_{t,n}^g$ have been determined by using 50 €/MWh as the upper bound and scaling it depending on the ratio between the actual and the average daily carbon emission intensity. The value $\gamma_{t,n}^d$ has been set to zero. Lithium-ion batteries with a 4-hour duration and 10 MW rated power have been assumed as reference storage. The average bid price in the TS auction has been set equal to the LCOS net of charging costs, which is equal to \$123.43 ((PNNL, 2024). We assume a maximum of $S_n^{TS} = 5$ GW of storage capacity per zone.

Table 2 reports the results by comparing a base case, and a test case that enforces the proposed scheme. The last column shows the percentage change in carbon emission per zone. As can be observed, almost all areas experience a significant carbon emission reduction, particularly the centre south (CSUD) zone, where the carbon intensity decreases by 13%. The only two zones where the carbon intensity slightly increases (by 1%) are the Centre North and North zones, as those zones are the ones with the lowest carbon emissions. At the country level, the total daily reduction is equal to 3,861 tCO₂, lowering the average emission intensity by 3.5%, i.e. from 189 kgCO₂ to 184 kgCO₂. Finally, Figure 1 visually depicts the values in the last column of Table 2.

Zone	Base Case			Test Case			Diff % kgCO ₂ /MWh
	kgCO ₂	MWh	kgCO ₂ /MWh	kgCO ₂	MWh	kgCO ₂ /MWh	
CALA	8,640,630	36,898	234	7,866,155	34,999	225	-4%
CNOR	7,170,528	43,293	166	7,362,821	43,822	168	1%
CSUD	9,803,278	64,874	151	8,047,592	61,358	131	-13%
NORD	44,642,076	270,121	165	45,888,608	273,734	168	1%
SARD	14,477,961	36,293	399	13,819,165	35,730	387	-3%
SICI	6,333,313	32,694	194	5,579,471	31,650	176	-9%
SUD	19,357,016	100,823	192	17,999,741	99,340	181	-6%
Total	110,424,802	584,996	189	106,563,553	580,633	184	-3%

Table 2 Carbon emissions in each market zone in the base case and in the test case where the proposed scheme is enforced.

Figure 1 Carbon emission changes in each market zone thanks to the proposed scheme.

5. Conclusion

In this study, we addressed the critical challenge of ensuring that energy storage operations align with decarbonisation objectives. We introduced and evaluated a novel carbon-aware mechanism within Italy's time-shifting market, designed to incentivise environmentally friendly charging and discharging patterns. The results from our simulation, based on actual market data, demonstrate the effectiveness of this approach. By providing financial signals tied to the grid's carbon intensity, the proposed scheme successfully reduced total carbon emissions, lowering the average emission intensity by 3.5%. Notably, significant reductions were observed in carbon-intensive regions, with decreases of up to 13%. These findings indicate that integrating explicit carbon-related incentives into market mechanisms for storage can be an effective strategy for policymakers to maximise the environmental benefits of energy storage investments and accelerate the transition towards net zero.

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